

TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANCE MINDSET IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF "SOFT SKILLS"

Umurzakova Dilfuza Ilhomovna

Fergana State University independent researcher

Phone: 998 91 106-24-37

e-mail: ilmymiy@inbox.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7939749>

Annotation : Special attention is paid to research on the rational use of "soft skills" opportunities in the teaching of foreign languages and the development of pedagogic mechanisms for the development of tolerant thinking in future foreign language teachers, a creative approach to education and the formation of a creative attitude. being directed. Because the quality and effectiveness of teaching foreign languages depends on the creative approach to the teaching process, cooperative pedagogy.

Key words: innovative educational technologies, tolerant thinking, creativity, innovation, innovative-creative, economic, social, cultural, humanitarian, tolerant, social activity.

There is an increasing need to develop the mindset and skills of tolerance in future foreign language teachers on the basis of innovative technologies, in particular through "soft skills". For this purpose, special emphasis is placed on the organization of innovative, creative and interesting lesson processes, interactive conversation, games and creative exercises in the nature of competitions. Through this, it will be possible to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages, to improve the educational technologies that serve the effectiveness of education, and to develop the thinking of creative tolerance and creativity and innovation skills in future teachers.

Therefore, special attention is paid to the organization of foreign education on the basis of "soft skills" in advanced foreign experience, and thereby to increase the quality of education, to create an atmosphere of creativity and tolerant relations. That is why the development of "soft skills" of tolerant thinking among future foreign language teachers is gaining relevance.

Many research works on the use of innovative educational technologies of modern pedagogy and the development of effective teaching methods are being carried out in the advanced scientific research institutes and international centers of the world. Special attention is paid to the research on the rational use of "soft skills" opportunities in the teaching of foreign languages and the development of the pedagogic mechanisms for the development of the mindset of tolerance in future foreign language teachers, the creative approach to education and the formation of a creative attitude. . Because it turns out that the quality and effectiveness of teaching foreign languages depends on a creative approach to the teaching process, cooperative pedagogy. Therefore, it is important to effectively use the possibilities of technology on the basis of "soft skills" in the development of the mindset of tolerance in future foreign language teachers.

In this regard, several researchers N. Mayorova, J. Renzulli, M. Runko, R. Sternberg, It has been researched by scientists such as E.Torrens, Drapeau Patti, Dj.Gilford. What is SOFT SKILLS? Why is it being equated with life and adaptability skills?

The origin of the concept of SOFT SKILLS goes back to issues related to the development of the military sector in the USA in 1959. According to him, when scientists conducted research on the competencies of military personnel, they considered it appropriate to divide skills into 2 types. They divide them into professional skills (hard skills) and personal qualities (soft skills). This is because they have determined that much of the success in war depends on how the soldiers in battle are led. In the educational programs, they are not taught to do this. However, working skills related to physical objects were formed. The measurement that exists in human thinking is complicated, its essence is not clear - it is related to soft skills. Currently, these words are more and more common in the Uzbek language in job applications. If we express these two concepts simply and concisely, we will have the following meaning: Hard skills can be mastered by studying at an educational institution. Examples of this include mastering a foreign language, programming, and driving skills. For this, it is enough to master the intelligent algorithmic instruction. In the process of mastering, the left hemisphere of the brain (logical) works more, and a high level of IQ (intelligence quotient) is necessary. (intelligence quotient) is required.

The acquisition of soft skills cannot be confirmed by any diploma. This is a person's resourcefulness, restraint, creativity, ability to adapt to the situation, not to lose oneself in stressful situations, and to adequately control one's actions. Mastering these skills requires the right hemisphere (creative) of the brain and a high level of EQ (intelligence quotient). (emotional intelligence) is preferable.

Thus, according to the ontogenetic logical development of a person, the concept of "life" skills can be used to determine psycho-pedagogical tasks for children of preschool and junior school age. At this stage, intensive development of individual aspects of a person, his prosocial and communicative skills, and self-management skills are inculcated.

Defining the concepts of "vital" and "adaptive" skills at the stages of education can be done on the basis of Bloom's taxonomy.

This ensures the success of the next stage of continuous education.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" publishing house, - B.464. 2021.
2. Decree No. PF-4947 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
3. United Nations World Declaration "Higher Education of the 21st Century" (1998), UNESCO Program Document "Reform and Development of Higher Education" (1995)
4. Akramova Sh.A. Modern pedagogical technologies and practical issues of their application in the educational process. Instructional manual. - Tashkent: OHBI, 2016. - 82 p
5. Riskulova K.D. Abstract of the dissertation "System of formation of sociolinguistic competence of future English language teachers". Tashkent 2017.
6. Jumanazarov. U. U. "Developing Linguistic Competence of Prospective English Language Teachers in an Environment of Digitization of Education". Dissertation abstract. Jizzakh 2021.